

CTD Processing Report for the July 2019 ASCA/ SEAmester survey

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1. Introduction

This is an extended report of the method used to correct the quality-controlled, processed CTD salinity data from the July 2019 ASCA/ SEAmester survey. We use these samples to correct the CTD data by following to the method described in the “Extended report on CTD processing for ASCA0618” by Shane Elipot. Unfortunately, at the time of the cruise, only 1 set of CTD sensors was available for the CTD. We are aware of the potential impacts this could have on the accuracy of the data collected. Other than the fact that we only have one set of sensors for comparison, this method for correcting the salinity data is identical to the correction method used on the previous ASCA/ SEAmester CTD surveys. The salinity samples collected from the Niskin bottles were processed during the cruise using the UCT Portasal by Jordan van Stavel and Laura Braby. The rough weather experienced on the cruise meant that we were only able to survey 16 out of the usual 20 ASCA CTD stations, from the shallowest station to a distance of approximately 200km from the coast.

2. Data

The CTD data were processed by James Maitland using the Sea-Bird software, after which we correct the salinity data. We use 116 salinity samples collected from the Niskin bottles, where 3 consecutive double conductivity ratio (X2R) readings from the Portasal did not differ by more than 0.002. The conductivity of the samples was then calculated using the TEOS-10 MATLAB toolbox and the median value of the 3 readings was taken as the final value for each sample.

Firstly, we compare the Standard Sea Water sample readings to the reference 2 x K15 values and determine if there is drift or offset in the Portasal values (Figure 1). Although very small,

we adjust the data accordingly.

Figure 1: a) The double conductivity ratio and b) the salinity for standard seawater samples showing the original values as read by the Portasal, the reference 2 x K15 value, the corrected values and the drift estimate.

We compare the salinity samples to the corresponding CTD values from the Niskin bottle files (Figure 2) and remove 5 obvious outliers from the dataset. We observe a slight negative bias in the data.

Figure 2: A scatter plot of Portasal and CTD salinity values. Portasal – Portasal values are indicated in black, Portasal- CTD1 values are in blue (5 large outliers have been removed).

3. Comparisons of Portasal and CTD conductivity values

For previous cruises, we have compared the conductivity values from the 2 sets of CTD sensors and removed any values where the difference is greater than 0.003 mS/cm. The number of values removed from the analysis ranged from 7-9 % of the samples. As we only had one set of sensors on the CTD for this survey, we have not removed any of the samples from the dataset.

We plot the difference between the CTD and Salinometer conductivity as functions of conductivity, pressure, time (or cast number) and temperature. Although no obvious trend is observed in the data, the negative bias observed in Figure 2 is also apparent in Figure 3. Table 1 below shows the slope and intercept of the data in Figure 3.

Table 1: The slope and y-intercept of the data represented in Figure 3 ($y = mx + c$)

Conductivity differences as a function of:	CTD 1 slope; intercept
Conductivity	-1.4840e-04; 0.0031
Pressure	-8.5795e-07; -0.0038
Cast Number	1.6895e-04; -0.0045
Temperature	-1.4394e-04; -0.0012

Figure 3: Conductivity differences between CTD and Portasal values and as a function of a) Conductivity, b) Pressure, c) Cast Number and d) Temperature.

4. Regression

As per the July 2016 and July 2018 ASCA/SEAmester CTD processing reports, we derive coefficients for the following correction models:

Model A: $C_C = \alpha C + \gamma$

Model AA: $C_C = \alpha C$

Model B: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta P + \gamma$

Model BB: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta P$

Model C: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta T + \gamma$

Model CC: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta T$

Model D: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta t + \gamma$

Model DD: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta t$

Where C represents conductivity, P represents pressure, T represents temperature and t represents time. α , β and γ are derived using the least squares method, regressing the CTD data against the sample calculated conductivity.

For all models the adjusted R^2 value almost equal to 1. Model DD reveals adjusted R^2 values that are slightly closer to 1 than the other models (Table 2). We therefore opt to correct the data according to model DD.

Table 2: Adjusted R squared values from the different models

Model	[1- Adjusted R²]
A	0.4137e-06
AA	0.4155e-06
B	0.4157e-06
BB	0.4119e-06
C	0.4140e-06
CC	0.4129e-06
D	0.4110e-06
DD	0.4074e-06

Figures 4 and 5 show a graphical representation of the results for the correction model DD, after large residuals have been removed. At first glance, we notice that the residuals are smaller than previous SEAmester cruises. Results from the regression are summarised in Table 3.

Figure 4: Results of regression for conductivity for model DD after removing large residuals.

Figure 5: Results of regression for salinity for model DD after removing large residuals.

Table 3: Results from second regression for conductivity and salinity for model DD

	Sensor Set 1
α	1.0001
β	-1.2167e-04
$\hat{\sigma}$ Conductivity (mS/cm)	0.0022
$\hat{\sigma}$ Salinity (PSU)	0.0020

$\hat{\sigma}$ is the square root of the mean square error (uncertainty). The estimate of the final error for conductivity is less than 3×10^{-3} mS/cm, which means that we have achieved the internationally acceptable standard. We further estimate $\hat{\sigma}$ for salinity and find that for model DD the error 0.0020 (the same as required accuracy of 0.002).

5. Finalising the data

We correct the quality-controlled processed CTD data from the July 2019 ASCA/ SEAmester survey according to model DD. Whilst we recognise that it would have been better to have 2 sets of CTD sensors for our survey, we are confident that we have achieved the internationally required accuracy for the salinity data. A T-S plot of the corrected data is shown in Figure 6. We observe that the data compares well with the data collected on the ACT surveys.

Figure 6: T-S diagram comparing the ACT data to the July 2019 ASCA/ SEAmester data. Dark blue, orange and yellow dots correspond to the ACT data. Purple dots indicate the uncorrected data, where as green dots show the data corrected according to model DD. Light blue dots are a T-S of the salinity sample data. The right hand panel is a close up of the left.